

D8.1 LIFE PRISTINE Communication and Dissemination Reports

(update M23)

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Deliverable Information Sheet

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Executive summary

The present public document presents an update of the LIFE PRISTINE Communication and Dissemination plans (PCP and PDP) outlined at M6, aiming at reaching as many relevant actors as possible to inform them on the activities and results derived from the project. EUT is responsible for designing and implementing LIFE PRISTINE communication and dissemination strategy, but all consortium partners are involved in it.

The channels and platforms considered in the communication and dissemination plan are: social media channels, official website, materials to be distributed in key events, media relations to specialized media outlets, scientific publications, the organization of workshops and local info-days, and attendance to strategic conferences, fairs and congresses where the project can be presented and the organisation of stakeholder engagement events, among others.

This deliverable updates the dissemination plan and reports on communication activities from M1 to M23.

[NOTE: Front page and Executive summary will be published in the website for all deliverables]

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
ACC	ACCIONA
CECs	Contaminants of Emerging Concern
DW	Drinking water
EC	European Commission
ESAMUR	Entidad de Saneamiento y Depuración de la Región de Murcia
EUT	Eurecat
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LR	Layman's Report
NXF	NX Filtration
PCP	PRISTINE Communication Plan
PDP	PRISTINE Dissemination Plan
VCI	Visual Corporate Identity
WP	Work Package
WW	Wastewater
XYL	Xylem

Introduction

The LIFE PRISTINE Communication and Dissemination Plan aims to outline the communication and dissemination activities planned throughout the project. These activities aim to **raise awareness** on the project and its **results** among the target audiences and as many relevant actors as possible, to **support exploitation** and to ensure market uptake of the developed solution, and to **share the know-how generated** from the project with the scientific and industrial community.

This document defines the tools and activities that have been carried out up until M23 of the project, as well as the upcoming activities to be carried out during the second period to ensure exposure and dissemination of the project itself and its results to the scientific and industrial community, in particular stakeholders in the water technologies sector.

Regarding the communication and dissemination actions done, this document presents the outcomes of LIFE PRISTINE activities and the impact achieved, including the creation of the project website and a set of promotional materials, the participation in events to raise awareness on the integrated PRISTINE solution or the production of the first press releases, to mention the main activities.

On the other hand, a plan for upcoming activities and a calendar is included, detailing the scope and goals of the forthcoming events to be organised, as well as events in which participation and scientific publications are planned.

All the actions in the plan consider the European Commission's requirements for funding recognition, as well as the recommendations and guidelines for communication and dissemination of LIFE programme projects¹.

The evaluation of the key performance indicators (KPIs) for each communication and dissemination activity at M23 are included to assess the progress made during the first project period.

¹ https://cinea.ec.europa.eu/programmes/life/communication-and-gdpr-rules_en

1 Communication and dissemination plan

EUT leads LIFE PRISTINE communication and dissemination activities within the project, but all consortium partners are actively involved in them. Dissemination and communication actions are considered by the consortium as a tool to accelerate the exploitation of results during and after the project as they help to raise awareness amongst key stakeholders.

The main goals behind LIFE PRISTINE Communication (PCP) and Dissemination Plan (PDP) are:

- **Raise awareness** on Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs), water technologies and the PRISTINE solution to permanently eliminate the compounds present in the water environment.
- Identify the project audience groups in terms of communication and dissemination activities, as well as the **main means and channels** that will be used to publicise the project to general public.
- **Support the exploitation** of project results and market uptake.
- **Share the know-how generated** from the project to the scientific and industrial community.
- **Establish a fluid two-way communication** to get real feedback on the competitiveness of the results.

LIFE PRISTINE communication and dissemination strategy aims at respecting partners' IPR and exploitation interests, with due care to not raise unrealistic expectations in end-users of the project solution, which may have a detrimental effect on market demand.

In the following sections, a description of target audiences, key messages and channels used and to be used are defined.

1.1 Target audience

Four stakeholder groups were identified at the beginning of the project execution as target audiences of the communication and dissemination activities, including: academia, industrial community, policy makers and the society at large. Detailed information is presented in Figure 1.

A list of key contacts and target stakeholders, in continuous update, is stored in the LIFE PRISTINE internal collaborative platform (ensuring that no personal information is included or distributed). This list has been regularly updated with new contacts, including individuals who sign-up to the project mailing list through a form circulated on the project communication channels.

Scientific and academic community

- Universities, research & technology organisations researching in water pollution, emerging contaminants, encapsulated adsorbents, advanced oxidation processes, membrane technologies and artificial intelligence based sensors
- Scientific associated media
- Attendees to trade exhibitions covering the project's fields (Water Innovation Europe, Stockholm Water Week, Singapore Water Week, Aquatec Amsterdam, WEFTEC Chicago, IEEXPo Shanghai, IFAT München, AMTA, etc.)

Industry, end users and customers

- Water sector, including water treatment plant operators and owners
- Industries in which the PRISTINE outcomes can be transferred or replicated (i.e. agri-food sector)
- Technology developers and providers, including the monitoring industry

Policy actors and decision makers

- Governmental bodies in charge of resources management (e.g. Departments of Environment)
- Networks associations (AWT, IWA, AEAS, etc.)
- Policy makers
- Decision makers
- Standardisation bodies and technical committees

Society at large

- General public and mass media
- EU citizens
- NGOs

Figure 1. Stakeholders groups

1.2 Channels

The dissemination and communication activities of the LIFE PRISTINE project use a wide range of channels and actions, ranging from publication of project results and news on the project website and social media channels, preparation of promotional materials, scientific publications, organisation of workshops, to the representation of the project in key events (see Figure 2).

Besides the aforementioned project channels, all partners have used and will make use of their own channels (websites, presence on social media and corporate newsletters / publications) to disseminate news about LIFE PRISTINE and reach a broader audience.

Figure 2. Communication and dissemination channels and activities

1.3 Key messages

Key messages defined in D8.1 Communication and Dissemination reports continue to be valid as the base messages to deliver to each of the stakeholder groups identified. If necessary, the messages will be tailored as the project advances, along with LIFE PRISTINE activities and results.

General LIFE PRISTINE messages include:

- LIFE PRISTINE focuses on developing an innovative solutions to remove contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from water treatment systems. By integrating cutting-edge technologies, the project aims to significantly enhance water quality and promote sustainable water management practices across various sectors.
- The core objective of LIFE PRISTINE is to safeguard public health and the environment by addressing the critical issue of water contamination. The project employs a multidisciplinary approach, combining advanced scientific research and practical applications to achieve its goals.

- At the heart of LIFE PRISTINE are innovative technologies such as adsorption capsule systems, low-energy HF-NF membrane arrangements, and AI-driven UV-led reactors. These methods are designed to efficiently and effectively remove a wide range of contaminants from water sources.
- The project is committed to fostering collaboration among experts, researchers, and industry professionals to tackle the challenges posed by contaminants of emerging concern. By sharing knowledge and resources, LIFE PRISTINE aims to drive progress in water treatment and environmental protection.
- LIFE PRISTINE not only addresses immediate water treatment needs but also contributes to the long-term sustainability of water resources. Through its innovative solutions and collaborative efforts, the project aims to ensure cleaner and safer water for both current and future generations.
- By focusing on holistic and sustainable approaches to water treatment, LIFE PRISTINE aims to set new standards in environmental and public health protection.

Academia

- LIFE PRISTINE contributes to the understanding of the environmental and health impacts of CECs. The project's research provides new insights into the behavior, persistence, seasonality and effects of these contaminants in various water ecosystems.
- The project's innovative methodologies include the integration of multiple treatment technologies into a cohesive system. This approach not only improves the removal efficiency of CECs but also offers a model for future research in integrated water treatment solutions.
- LIFE PRISTINE generates extensive empirical data on the performance of advanced water treatment technologies under real-world conditions. This data is invaluable for advancing theoretical models and practical applications in the field of environmental science and engineering.

Industry, consumers and end users

- LIFE PRISTINE develops advanced water treatment solutions specifically designed to improve water quality and eliminate CECs. These solutions can be transferred to other industrial processes in order to obtain safe and clean reclaimed water, free from CECs.
- The project's technologies are tailored to provide cost-effective and efficient methods for removing CECs, helping industries maintain high standards of water quality while minimizing operational costs. This is particularly important for sectors that rely heavily on water for production and processing.

- LIFE PRISTINE's integrated technology solution includes innovative methods such as low-energy HF-NF membrane arrangements and AI-driven UV-led reactors. These technologies are designed to enhance the effectiveness of water treatment processes, ensuring that end users receive water that meets safety and quality standards.
- The project also focuses on helping industries comply with regulatory standards related to water quality and environmental protection. By adopting LIFE PRISTINE's solution, businesses can improve their compliance and reduce their environmental footprint, contributing to more sustainable practices.
- LIFE PRISTINE's advancements mean access to safer, higher-quality water for everyday use. The project's efforts to remove CECs from water sources ensure that the water used for drinking, cooking, and other household activities is free from harmful contaminants.
- LIFE PRISTINE provides end users, including municipalities and water utilities, with the tools and knowledge needed to implement effective water management strategies, ultimately leading to better water quality for the communities they serve.

Policy actors and decision makers

- LIFE PRISTINE supports policy development by identifying and promoting the best technologies for removing contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from water. The research and project findings offer insights that can inform policy decisions and regulatory frameworks.
- The project emphasizes the importance of effective CEC monitoring and water treatment methods. By providing data and evidence-based recommendations, LIFE PRISTINE aims to assist policymakers in developing regulations that ensure high standards of water quality and public health protection.
- LIFE PRISTINE collaborates with policy actors to influence the development of regulations that promote the adoption of innovative water treatment solutions. The project advocates for policies that support sustainable practices and address the challenges posed by CECs in water sources.
- LIFE PRISTINE aligns its objectives with global sustainable development goals, particularly those related to clean water and sanitation. The project advocates for policy actions that support the implementation of advanced water treatment technologies, ensuring cleaner, safer water for all.

Society at large

- LIFE PRISTINE improves water quality for communities and ecosystems by developing advanced solutions to remove CECs from water sources. The project's efforts aim to protect public health and the environment.
- The project raises awareness about the impact of everyday consumption habits on water treatment and quality. By educating the public on the presence of CECs in various products and encouraging responsible consumption, LIFE PRISTINE promotes healthier lifestyles and environmental protection.
- The project's initiatives advocate for cleaner, safer water for future generations. By addressing current water contamination challenges, LIFE PRISTINE aims to ensure that future generations have access to high-quality water resources.

2 Communication and dissemination management

2.1 Distribution of responsibilities

The LIFE PRISTINE dissemination and communication strategy foresees the active involvement and commitment of all project partners for presenting the project and its main outcomes.

WP8 Communication & Raise awareness includes the following tasks related to communication and dissemination tasks with the following objectives:

- **Task 8.1 Communication and dissemination plan (M1-M6)**
 - Development of LIFE PRISTINE Communication Plan (PCP) and Dissemination Plan (PDP)
- **Task 8.2 Communication activities (M1-M48)**
 - Set up LIFE PRISTINE communication channels
 - Generate awareness on the project, its findings and economic / environmental impact
 - Inform and promote project activities and results to broad audiences
 - Support project exploitation and results' market uptake
 - Transfer knowledge and results to the industrial and scientific community
- **Task 8.3 Networking activities**
 - Ensure wide and transversal dissemination of project activities
 - Organisation of project meetings, technical forums/workshops and conferences

EUT, through its Research Communication Office (RCO) is the Communication and Dissemination lead beneficiary, responsible for coordinating WP8 activities, ensuring the proper information exchange within the consortium and supporting the full communication and dissemination of the project and its results.

All partners will contribute to ensure the successful implementation of the communication and dissemination activities and the reach to the different stakeholder groups identified.

2.2 Requirements

All communication and dissemination materials produced in the project (posters, presentations, promotional materials, publications, etc.) and distributed in physical or electronic format will display the EU emblem and funding text provided below, in line with the EU regulations described in the Grant Agreement.

According to the Grant Agreement “*unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:*

- a) *Display the EU emblem*
- b) *Include the following text*

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union

Figure 3. Funding acknowledgement

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Additionally, according to the Grant Agreement, *Communication activities and infrastructure, equipment or major results funded by the grant must moreover display the LIFE Programme logo:*

Figure 4. LIFE Programme flag

2.3 Monitoring and reporting

2.3.1 Activities reporting

Following a specific methodology applied to all European Projects, EUT Research Communication Office created an Excel file to register all dissemination and communication activities done by partners during project execution.

This file, located in the Microsoft Teams online repository is available to all partners (WP8 - Communication and raise awareness - 00_Reporting - KPI_Reporting_PRISTINE) contains, among others, a description of dissemination activity, type and size of audience, date and location, partner/s involved and feedback received, among others.

LIFE PRISTINE Dissemination activities						
Dissemination action	Status	Dates	Event name	Type of audience	Size of audience	Place
Participation to a Congress / Exhibition	Attended	October 17, 2022	Congress of Spanish Young Water Professionals (IWA)	Industry Community	TBD	Valencia, Spain
Participation to a Workshop	Attended	February 1, 2023	ISLE-Água Utilities Webinar Series	Industry Community	TBD	Online
Participation to an Event other than a Conf	Attended	February 10, 2023	1000Riques	Other	60	Granollers, Spain
Participation to a Workshop	Attended	March 15-16, 2023	XV Jornadas Técnicas de Reutilización de Agua Regenerada. Nuevos retos, nuevas soluciones	TBD	TBD	Cartagena, Spain
Participation to an Event other than a Conf	Attended	May 10, 2023	Webinar on the LIFE Programme 2023 call	TBD	TBD	Online
Organisation of a Workshop / Conference	Attended	May 30-31, 2023	IDEAS 2023	TBD	TBD	Bilbao, Spain
Participation to a Congress / Exhibition	Attended	June 13-15, 2023	XIII AEDYR International Congress	Industry Community	TBD	Granada, Spain
Participation to a Conference	Attended	June 26-29, 2023	6th IWA International Conference on eco-Technologies for Wastewater Treatment	Industry Community	TBD	Girona, Spain
Participation to a Workshop	Cancelled	February 2024	Workshop on PFAS problematic	TBD	TBD	Barcelona, Spain
Participation to a Workshop	Attended	March 19, 2024	Scientific communication workshop - Catalan Water Partnership (CWP)	TBD	TBD	Barcelona, Spain
Participation to a Congress / Exhibition	Abstract accepted	June 5-7, 2024	XXXVII Congreso AEAS	TBD	TBD	Castellón, Spain
Participation to a Conference	Abstract submitted	June 24-26, 2024	LET2024: 19th IWA Leading Edge Conference on Water and Wastewater Technologies	TBD	TBD	Essen, Germany
Participation to a Conference	Abstract submitted	June 16-19, 2024	IWA YWP Conference 2024	TBD	TBD	Prague, Czech Republ
Participation to an Event other than a Conf	Abstract submitted	September 18-19, 2024	XIV Jornadas de Comunicación y Divulgación Científicas	TBD	TBD	Barcelona, Spain
Participation to a Conference	Abstract submitted	March 16-20, 2025	14th IWA International Conference on Water Reclamation and Reuse	TBD	TBD	Cape Town, South Afr

Figure 5. View of reporting activities table

Separately, a folder titled “Events” was created. After a dissemination event takes place (organised or attended by LIFE PRISTINE project partners), a folder with the name of the event is created inside the “Events” folder with the dissemination materials presented (poster, presentation, promotional materials, etc.) and some photographic evidence on the dissemination action.

Figure 6. View of the "Events" folder within Microsoft Teams

2.3.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

KPIs have been assigned to several communication and dissemination activities planned in the project to assess their performance and impact by the end of the project. The main KPIs established are listed in Table 1. See below the status of the KPIs set at M23, during the month of production of this deliverable. The values expected to be achieved in M48 are also included.

Table 1. Communication and Dissemination KPIs

Strategy	Target Group	Objective	M23	M48
Project logo, visuals, presentation templates	All	Creating a common visual identity	1	1
Interactive digital platform (# of total website visits by the end of the project)	All	Main entry point to the project, repository of news and public contents	611*	10,000
Social Media (# of Twitter and LinkedIn followers)	All	Interaction and engagement with online communities. Managed by local partners in local languages	206	500
(# of tweets and LinkedIn posts)			133	250

Project Brochures / Leaflets				
(# of brochures created)	All	Communication materials to be distributed at events	1	2
(# of brochures / leaflets distributed)			0	500
Media coverage				
(# of press releases / articles)	All	Project related news for the media.	2	8
Social awareness campaigns				
(# of released campaigns)	All	Social media campaigns to inform about CECs origin, impact, and treatment	0	3
Annual Newsletter				
(# of newsletters)	All	These newsletters may include interviews and other relevant related articles.	1	4
(# of digital subscribers)			35	200
Videos				
(# of project videos)	All	Short videos presenting the project features	2	2
(# of video views)			132	2,000
Informative publications				
(# of informative articles)	All	Independent articles about the project published in trade magazines focusing on either: overview of the project, advantages of proposed solutions, etc.	2	4
Policy related events				
(# of European and national/regional event participation)	Policy actors & decision makers	Participation in future policy making improvement to regulate CECs.	0	3
Scientific Conferences	Policy actors and decision makers, Industry (Water utilities, Technology providers), Research & Academia			
(# of conference publications)		Participation in events presenting the project	2	4
EU Events, Trade Fairs, Projects & Workshops				
(# of events)	Policy actors and decision makers, Industry, Research & Academia	Participation in events presenting the project	11	4
(# of project workshops)			0	1
			N/A	50

(# of participants in organised events)				
International Journals (# of journal publications)	Policy actors and decision makers, Industry (Water utilities, Technology providers), Research & Academia	Presentation of project results	0	4
Related Project Exchanges (# of networking meetings together)	Industry (Water utilities, Technology providers), Research & Academia	Networking with other projects to explore synergies and lessons learnt	4	8
Final Event (# of attendees)	All	Raise awareness of the project and its results	N/A	200

*The website follows the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) directive, which came into force on October 31st, 2020. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics can only be tracked for users accepting analytic cookies. Estimating that only about 30% of the users accept the cookies before starting to browse the website, and considering that this 30% accounts for the data retrieved, we can estimate that we have received around 1425 additional visits that couldn't be tracked. The same calculations can be extrapolated to the number of pages viewed, denoting that the project website has had more impact than what the statistics recorded through Google Analytics show.

2.4 Risks and mitigation measures

The following table presents risks faced in the completion of activities planned in WP8 and potential mitigation measures:

Table 2. Risks and mitigation measures

Risks	Risk level	Mitigation measures
#1 - Low stakeholder engagement	Medium	Identify key stakeholders and establish regular communication channels. Use stakeholder mapping to tailor engagement strategies. Organise periodic stakeholder meetings and workshops to gather feedback and keep them informed.
#2 - Limited public awareness and outreach	Low	Develop a comprehensive public outreach plan that includes social media, press releases, and community events. Collaborate with local media and influencers to amplify project messages. Create engaging and

		accessible content to educate the public about the project's goals and achievements.
#3 - Miscommunication of technical information	Medium	Simplify complex technical information into clear, concise messages for non-expert audiences. Use visual aids and infographics to help convey technical concepts.
#4 - Insufficient dissemination of project results to the academic community	Medium	Publish research findings in high-impact, peer-reviewed journals. Present results at international conferences and workshops. Use academic networks and platforms to share findings widely. Engage with academic societies and organisations to facilitate the dissemination of results.

3 PRISTINE Communication Plan (PCP)

The following sections include a list of the different communication activities, tools and actions planned for the LIFE PRISTINE project (Corporate Visual Identity, website, promotional materials, social media, press releases, etc.).

All the communication actions and channels planned are and will be continuously aligned with the dissemination of the activities and project's results and will follow the calendar of the project's execution and its milestones and achievements.

3.1 Project Visual Corporate Identity materials

EUT has been in charge of defining the project's image to be implemented across all the communication and dissemination channels, including the design of the logo, colour palette, and deliverable and presentation templates. EUT will ensure the correct use of the visual identity in all project-related materials. For more information regarding the LIFE PRISTINE visual identity, refer to D8.1 Communication and Dissemination reports delivered on M6.

3.2 Website

The project website (<https://eurecat.org/en/portfolio-items/life-pristine/>) was launched in October 2022. It has served since its creation as the main information platform for users interested in knowing more about LIFE PRISTINE. The website displays the project's basic information, objectives, demonstration scenarios and expected outputs. Furthermore, the website is the central repository for all public material, including public results and deliverables, and provides access to the project's X, LinkedIn and YouTube channels.

The website has been regularly updated by EUT with dissemination activities, media appearances and new deliverables, among other materials. For more information regarding LIFE PRISTINE public website, refer to deliverable **D8.2 LIFE PRISTINE website**.

PRISTINE in a nutshell

Removing Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams thanks to the PRISTINE Integrated Solution

Figure 7. LIFE PRISTINE website

A total of 3 project news articles on project activities and 10 articles on events have been published on the project website, curated by Eurecat.

For the second period of the project, new sections will be created and updated following project activities and milestones, including detailed information on each demonstration site, the scientific production or articles on dissemination activities and results.

NEWS & EVENTS

<div style="background-color: #008080; color: white; padding: 5px; font-weight: bold;">20</div> <div style="font-size: small; color: #008080;">03, 2024</div>		<p>Eurecat presents LIFE PRISTINE at a workshop on science communication in the water management sector March 20th, 2024</p> <p>Marina Pressas, Communication and Dissemination Officer from Eurecat, has participated in a workshop on science communication in the water management sector organised by the Catalan Water Partnership on March 19th, 2024, at the Catalonia Rambles Hotel in Barcelona (Spain). During the event, the communication strategy implemented in LIFE PRISTINE, [...]</p>
<div style="background-color: #008080; color: white; padding: 5px; font-weight: bold;">16</div> <div style="font-size: small; color: #008080;">01, 2024</div>		<p>LIFE PRISTINE unveils insights from water analytical campaign: five families of Contaminants of Emerging Concern arise as primary focus January 16th, 2024</p> <p>The LIFE PRISTINE analytical campaign has made it possible to select a total of 17 relevant compounds that will constitute the shortlist of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) that will be followed during the PRISTINE solution demonstration. These 17 relevant compounds are classified as pharmaceuticals, pesticides, industrial chemicals, microplastics [...]</p>
<div style="background-color: #008080; color: white; padding: 5px; font-weight: bold;">29</div> <div style="font-size: small; color: #008080;">06, 2023</div>		<p>Exhibition of a poster based on LIFE PRISTINE research at the ecoSTP conference June 29th, 2023</p> <p>Aina Soler Jofra, project partner from ACCIONA, has shared LIFE PRISTINE knowledge at the 6th IWA International Conference on eco-Technologies for Wastewater Treatment (ecoSTP 2023), celebrated on Girona (Spain) on June 26th-29th. During the event, she exhibited a poster entitled "Innovative and versatile integrated solution to remove contaminants of emerging concern [...]"</p>

Figure 8. News & events section

3.2.1 Website analytics M1-M23

The LIFE PRISTINE website uses Google Analytics and Matomo to monitor all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site’s performance.

Table 3. Website analytics (M1-M23)

Website indicator	M1-M23
Visits	611*
Users	265
Actions per visit	2,1
Average visit duration (min)	0:48

*The website follows the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) directive, which came into force on October 31st, 2020. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics can only be tracked for users accepting analytic cookies. Estimating that only about 30% of the users accept the cookies before starting to browse the website, and considering that this 30% accounts for the data retrieved, we can estimate that we have received around 1425 additional visits that couldn’t be tracked. The same calculations can be extrapolated to the number of pages viewed, denoting that the project website has had more impact than what the statistics recorded through Google Analytics show.

3.3 Promotional materials

EUT has been in charge of creating a set of visual materials to support the project’s dissemination activities and events, such as conferences, congresses, workshops or project events.

All materials are stored digitally in the project’s internal repository and on the project’s website for broader dissemination. Promotional materials will be regularly updated according to the project’s developments.

3.3.1 General project materials

EUT has crafted communication materials such as a **general brochure** (M5), a **roll-up** and an **A1 poster**. In the second half of the project, a **technical brochure** will be developed (M25-36).

All materials produced follow the project’s visual identity guidelines and are available to all consortium members in a digital and ready-to-print format. The materials are also available publicly on the project’s website in the section “Project materials”.

Figure 9. LIFE PRISTINE promotional materials

3.3.2 Audiovisual materials

Engaging videos are planned to present the key aspects of the project. The videos produced within the project are published on the LIFE PRISTINE website and social media channels, as well as in the YouTube channel.

These videos will summarise challenges of CECs, project’s objectives, proposed solutions through AI and expected results, showcasing images and end user testimonies with all success cases obtained during demos.

The production of other audiovisual materials will be evaluated among the consortium if any other opportunities arise. Partners will be able to propose other video topics and produce complementary videos on their contribution to the LIFE PRISTINE project.

The videos uplodaded up to M23 include the project’s animated video and a presentation of the project during a webinar by Ana Jiménez-Banzo, project’s coordinator from ACCIONA.

- [Presentation of the LIFE PRISTINE project during an Isle Utilities webinar](#)
- [LIFE PRISTINE - Integrated solution to remove contaminants of emerging concern in water streams](#)

Figure 10. Recording of a LIFE PRISTINE presentation

Figure 11. LIFE PRISTINE animated video

All planned videos have been and will be produced in English, with subtitles available to facilitate comprehension. In the second period of the project, more videos are planned to disseminate the results of the project showcasing real images of the demonstration sites, among others.

3.4 Social media strategy

EUT manages LIFE PRISTINE’s social media accounts and its content, consisting of an X, (@PRISTINE_EU), LinkedIn (LIFE PRISTINE) and YouTube channels (LIFE PRISTINE).

On the other hand, partners are contributing to spreading the word on their corporate and personal social media channels, including accounts in Facebook, X, LinkedIn, YouTube or Instagram.

The project coordinator is in charge of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels and, whenever possible, will promote the use of social media complicities between LIFE PRISTINE and its sister projects.

The typology of content published in LIFE PRISTINE social media accounts has included:

- **Disseminating project activities:** sharing information on stakeholder engagement events, workshops, technical webinars and other dissemination activities, including text and pictures if possible.
- **Disseminating audiovisual and promotional materials** produced (to make the project more accessible/understandable).
- **Promoting** the project community of interest.
- **Sharing news and articles published on the website** to increase traffic.
- **Content curation:** sharing news on CECs or water directives and policies, among others.

3.4.1 X

LIFE PRISTINE project’s main objective on X is to raise awareness on CECs and water technologies, as well as promoting the benefits of the project’s solution.

X is also being used to connect with EU institutions and related projects and initiatives. Relevant stakeholders and partners with a professional X account have been followed by the LIFE PRISTINE account in order to boost the visibility of the account.

EUT has populated the account with content with inputs of consortium partners. For promoting specific events/campaigns, the posts published included some graphical material created specially to make them more appealing. A Hootsuite profile, a tool facilitating the publication of content and activity monitoring, has been created for scheduling posts and shortening URLs. Comments and answers have been managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

In D8.1 Communication and Dissemination reports delivered in M6, a content strategy was developed, mixing marketing content, branding and influence actions to maximise the project's impact, and encourage market uptake to secure a critical mass of early adopters of the PRISTINE Integrated Solution. At M23, the strategy continues being valid and serves as guideline for all project partners posting about the project on social media.

Figure 12. Examples of posts in X

A profile in X Analytics was activated at the beginning of the project in order to measure the X KPIs and other data about the account activity.

Figure 13. X analytics profile

As a result of all the activity, at M23 LIFE PRISTINE X has 93 followers and has generated 81 posts and more than 6600 impressions and 22 mentions.

Table 4. X analytics (M1-M23)

X indicator	M1-M23
Followers	93
Tweets posted	81

Impressions	6644
Mentions	22
Likes on Tweets	84
Retweets	36

3.4.2 LinkedIn

On the other hand, LinkedIn is a platform for the interaction among professionals to exchange experiences to improve their work placement. LIFE PRISTINE account on LinkedIn, created at M2, allows project partners to connect with the industrial and academic community, as well as connect and engage with professionals and stakeholders from the water sector.

Content creation in this account follows the social media guidelines specified in *D8.1 Communication and Dissemination Reports*, although the publication pace in LinkedIn is less frequent than in X. Content is based on project news, events organised and participated, and reports and publications produced in the framework of the project or by trusted sources.

The LinkedIn account is managed by EUT. All consortium partners can propose contents (text, images, videos...) to be distributed through this channel and can spread the word through their own corporate and personal channels by sharing the content published.

Publishing, as well as comments, answers and private messages are managed manually, in order to facilitate the removal of potential fake users or spam content.

Data on publications' impact will be retrieved from LinkedIn Analytics. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the next update of this deliverable.

LIFE PRISTINE

Innovative and versatile integrated solution to remove contaminants of emerging concern in water treatment systems

Sistemas de suministro de agua e irrigación · Barcelona · 109 seguidores · 11-50 empleados

Figure 14. LIFE PRISTINE LinkedIn profile

By M23, the LIFE PRISTINE LinkedIn profile has 113 followers, 52 posts published and more than 15.400 impressions.

Table 5. LinkedIn analytics (M1-M23)

LinkedIn indicator	M1-M23
Followers	113
Posts published	52

Impressions	15456
Shares	42
Reactions	570

3.4.3 YouTube

The European Commission recommends the use of audiovisual resources as the storytelling for putting objectives and results of the research projects closer to the general public.

Following these recommendations, the videos produced within the project are allocated in a **YouTube channel** and will be shared on the website and project’s X and LinkedIn for a broader impact.

Figure 15. LIFE PRISTINE YouTube channel

Data on videos views and channels subscribers is being collected from YouTube analytics. At M23, the account counts with 2 videos available. From the creation of the account in M5, LIFE PRISTINE YouTube channel has received 130 views and 3 watch time hours.

Tu canal ha conseguido 130 visualizaciones hasta ahora

Figure 16. YouTube analytics (M1-M23)

3.4.4 Partners' channels

Most of the partners have shared LIFE PRISTINE news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (X, LinkedIn, Facebook...), including press releases, news about events, promotional materials and other contents published in the project's website or in the X account.

LIFE PRISTINE's partners impact in social media channels will reach more than **185K users on Twitter**, more than **252K on LinkedIn** and more than **41K Facebook** followers.

The corporate accounts used by partners are:

Table 6. Partner's social media channels

PARTNER	Facebook	Twitter	LinkedIn	Instagram
ACC	N/A	@ACCIONA	http://www.linkedin.com/showcase/accionagua	N/A
EUT	https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/	@Eurecat_news	https://www.linkedin.com/company/eurecat/	N/A
NXF	N/A	N/A	https://www.linkedin.com/company/nx-filtration/	N/A

ESAMUR	https://www.facebook.com/esamuraguas/	@ESAMUR_Aguas	https://www.linkedin.com/company/esamuraguas/	https://www.instagram.com/esamuraguas/
XYLEM	https://www.facebook.com/XylemIncorporated/	@Xylem	https://www.linkedin.com/company/xylem-inc/	https://www.instagram.com/xylem_inc/

Figure 17. Examples of posts in partners' channels

3.4.5 Awareness raising campaigns

Three awareness raising campaigns are envisaged during the course of the project. These campaigns will include information about the presence of CECs in the environment and the efforts of the water sector towards their removal. They will also suggest simple gestures to reduce the emissions of CECs into the environment.

Additionally, the campaigns will also be promoted through ACC and LIFE PRISTINE project websites.

3.5 Media relations

Press releases will be written and sent throughout the project focusing on the release of research results, project milestones, attendance at specialised events, conferences, etc.

All press releases will be distributed among partners in English for providing feedback (where appropriate), giving them the opportunity to adapt the documents in their corporate language and to circulate it among their regional media contacts.

Apart from consortium press releases, country-focused press releases or press releases oriented to a specific stakeholder group may be elaborated by partners, after informing the Project Coordinator and Communication Leader (EUT). Also, LIFE PRISTINE partners will consider interview-offerings and a press conference at the end of the project to showcase the main project results to the media.

In the framework of the project, a **database with the contact details of partners' communication officers has been created**, to facilitate the review of the media materials, coordinate the sending of the press release and increase the project's impact across European media outlets.

During the project, a **minimum of 4 informative publications are planned in trade magazines, such as the listed in table 7**. The calendar, partner responsible, and magazine selection, as well as the tracking media appearances, will be discussed at partners meetings.

The objective is for a wide range of readers to reach the project topics involved in academia, as well as industry. A list of European and global specialised media outlets identified as relevant to promote LIFE PRISTINE outputs include:

Table 7. Specialised outlets of interest

Outlet name	Website	Language
iAgua	https://www.iagua.es/	Spanish
RETEMA	https://www.retema.es/	Spanish
Aguas Residuales	https://www.aguasresiduales.info/	Spanish
FuturEnviro	https://futurenviro.es/	Spanish
DWA KA Korrespondenz Abwasser	http://de.dwa.de/de/ka-korrespondenz-abwasser-abfall.html	German
DVGW Publications	https://www.dvgw.de/leistungen/publikationen	German
Gwf Wasser/Abwasser	https://gwf-wasser.de/gwf-wasser-abwasser/	German
EUWID Wasser Abwasser	https://www.euwid-wasser.de/	German
Water Europe	https://watereurope.eu/news/	English
Water News Europe	https://www.waternewseurope.com/	English

3.5.1 Press releases produced

During M1 - M23, LIFE PRISTINE Communication and Dissemination leader EUT produced two press releases with general information about the project and its consortium which was distributed to all partners.

- Consortium press release (M3): <https://eurecat.org/en/acciona-leads-an-initiative-to-eliminate-emerging-pollutants-in-the-end-to-end-water-cycle/>
- Results of the analytical campaign for demo sites characterisation (M16): <https://eurecat.org/en/life-pristine-unveils-insights-from-water-analytical-campaign-five-families-of-contaminants-of-emerging-concern-arise-as-primary-focus/>

Figure 18. Press releases published on the LIFE PRISTINE website

EUT wrote the first press release with the inputs of all the project’s partners and sent it to general media outlets as well as specialised magazine and journals.

Based on this press release, partners also adapted and/or translated their own versions.

- EUT (Catalan): [Eurecat participa en una iniciativa liderada per Acciona per a l’eliminació de contaminants emergents en el cicle integral de l’aigua](#)
- EUT (Spanish): [Eurecat participa en una iniciativa liderada por Acciona para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua](#)
- NXF (English): [NX Filtration part of ACCIONA-led initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources](#)
- ACC (Spanish): [ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua](#)
- ESAMUR (Spanish): [Los socios del proyecto LIFE PRISTINE investigan cómo eliminar los contaminantes emergentes del agua](#)

Enschede, the Netherlands, 11 October 2022

NX Filtration part of ACCIONA-led initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources

NX Filtration, the global provider of breakthrough direct nanofiltration technology for pure and affordable water, announces its participation in the European innovation project LIFE PRISTINE, led by ACCIONA S.A. The project's objective is to eliminate emerging contaminants in the integral water cycle, one of the essential measures to promote alternative water resources in the face of water scarcity, which affects more than 2.8 billion people worldwide.

The LIFE PRISTINE project has a budget of 4 million euros and is coordinated by ACCIONA, the Spanish sustainable infrastructure solutions group. Next to ACCIONA and NX Filtration, project partners include Eurecat, Xylem Services, the Regional Entity for Wastewater Sanitation and Treatment of the Murcia Region (ESAMUR) and the water utility provider Ribao Inha Water Consortium (CABB).

The LIFE PRISTINE project combines water treatment processes, including NX Filtration's hollow fiber nanofiltration membranes, with artificial intelligence-based digital tools to develop a solution that removes emerging pollutants in the integrated water cycle. The integrated and versatile PRISTINE solution will be demonstrated in a representative full-scale operational environment.

Figure 19. Press releases published on partners' websites

3.5.2 Media impacts

As result of this action, LIFE PRISTINE project was featured in a total of **27 impacts in generalist and specialised media outlets** at local, regional, national and international level.

Table 8. LIFE PRISTINE media impacts (M1-M23)

DATE	MEDIA	TITLE	TYPE	LANGUAGE	LINK
05/10/2022	Smart Water Magazine	ACCIONA leads an initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants in end-to-end water cycle	Online	English	Link
05/10/2022	iAgua	ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para eliminar contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
05/10/2022	Retema	ACCIONA lidera LIFE PRISTINE para eliminar contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
06/10/2022	FuturENVIRO	ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
06/10/2022	Aguasresiduales.info	ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para la eliminación de Contaminantes Emergentes en el Ciclo Integral del Agua	Online	Spanish	Link
07/10/2022	TecnoAqua	Acciona lidera una iniciativa para eliminar contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
09/10/2022	Aqua Tech	EU COLLABORATION LINKS MEMBRANES & AI TO TARGET EMERGING POLLUTANTS	Online	English	Link
11/10/2022	Obras Urbanas	Iniciativa para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
12/10/2022	Water & Wastewater Asia	NX Filtration to be part of Acciona-led initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources	Online	English	Link

13/10/2022	Filtration + Separation	NX Filtration joins European initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources	Online	English	Link
23/11/2022	Aguasresiduales.info	Ana Jiménez-Banzo, coordinadora del LIFE PRISTINE nos comenta todos los detalles de este proyecto sobre CEC	Online	Spanish	Link
23/05/2023	EFE Verde	Gestión eficiente de agua, recuperación o captación, cómo luchar contra la sequía	Online	Spanish	Link
18/06/2023	La Vanguardia	El desafío de lograr un agua 'pristine', sin contaminantes	Print	Spanish	Link
18/06/2023	La Vanguardia	El desafío de lograr un agua 'pristine', sin contaminantes	Online	Spanish	Link
27/11/2023	iAgua	El proyecto LIFE PRISTINE investiga cómo eliminar los contaminantes emergentes del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
30/11/2023	Retema	Avanza el proyecto LIFE PRISTINE hacia la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
16/01/2024	OK Diario	Detectan 17 tipos de contaminantes emergentes en el agua antes de ser tratada para su consumo	Online	Spanish	Link
16/01/2024	Aguasresiduales.info	El proyecto europeo LIFE PRISTINE identifica a cinco familias principales de contaminantes emergentes en el agua	Online	Spanish	Link
17/01/2024	Interempresas	El proyecto Life Pristine identifica cinco familias principales de contaminantes emergentes en el agua	Online	Spanish	Link
18/01/2024	Ecoticias	Proyecto europeo LIFE PRISTINE: objetivo eliminar los contaminantes emergentes presentes en el ciclo del agua	Online	Spanish	Link
29/01/2024	Interempresas	Más de medio centenar de depuradoras murcianas cuentan con tratamiento con luz ultravioleta	Online	Spanish	Link
08/02/2024	iAgua	Murcia acoge la planta piloto en la que Europa estudiará la última tecnología en depuración	Online	Spanish	Link
12/02/2024	Retema	Región de Murcia acoge una planta piloto que estudiará la última tecnología en depuración de agua	Online	Spanish	Link

13/02/2024	Retema	El motor de la economía circular del agua: la depuración deja paso a las biofactorías	Online	Spanish	Link
01/06/2024	Cadena SER	Un proyecto piloto de ESAMUR en Ceutí avanza en la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el agua residual	Online	Spanish	Link
01/06/2024	Cadena SER	Un proyecto piloto de ESAMUR en Ceutí avanza en la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el agua residual	Radio	Spanish	Link
01/06/2024	Global Water Intelligence	ACCIONA's initiative related to emerging pollutants	Online	English	Link

3.5.3 Press release plan

The planned calendar for upcoming press releases is as follows:

Table 9. LIFE PRISTINE press release plan

LIFE PRISTINE press release plan		Partners responsible
M26	Development and fine-tuning of individual technologies, process models and DSS	EUT, ACC, NXF, XYL
M35	Demonstration of the PRISTINE Integrated Solution in a wastewater treatment real scenario	ALL
M47	Demonstration of the PRISTINE Integrated Solution in a drinking water treatment real scenario	ALL
M48	Final project results	EUT, ACC, distributed in partners regions
TBD	Participation in a relevant event	TBD
TBD	TBD	TBD

3.6 Newsletters

News and updates of the project will be distributed via newsletters to ensure that all stakeholders are regularly informed about the latest project's developments.

The database of subscribers will be built during the whole project, putting the main efforts during the first months of the project to have an acceptable number of subscribers for the first release.

Up to M23, the first newsletter was released on M12. In this first issue, contents included information on the project’s objectives and expected results, the PRISTINE Integrated Solution, a selection of media articles featuring LIFE PRISTINE and the latest events attended by project partners.

Hello!

Welcome to the first newsletter of the [LIFE PRISTINE](#) project.

The PRISTINE Integrated Solution aims to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams.

In this issue, you will be able to find about:

- What is the LIFE PRISTINE project, main objectives and expected results.
- The PRISTINE Integrated Solution.
- A selection of media articles featuring LIFE PRISTINE.
- The latest dissemination activities and events attended by project's partners.

We hope you enjoy reading our newsletter and invite you to check our website regularly, follow us on social media or contact us directly for more information at lifepristineproject@gmail.com

LIFE PRISTINE at a quick glance!

LIFE PRISTINE project aims to develop the PRISTINE Integrated Solution to remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from water streams.

The PRISTINE Integrated Solution will be adaptable on a case-by-case basis for drinking water (DW), to protect humans from CECs, and for wastewater (WW), to protect the environment and remove these contaminants from the water cycle.

Figure 20. LIFE PRISTINE first newsletter

Three additional newsletters will be issued in the second part of the project:

Table 10. Newsletter schedule

LIFE PRISTINE newsletters schedule	
2 nd Newsletter	M24
3 rd Newsletter	M36
4 th Newsletter	M48

The LIFE PRISTINE newsletters will be disseminated via links on social media, direct ad hoc emails to professional contacts of the consortium partners and via browsing the LIFE PRISTINE website, where all issues will be stored.

Furthermore, information about LIFE PRISTINE project will be included to partners' newsletters or corporate publications, such as EUT's monthly corporate newsletter addressed to external audience, with more than 15,000 subscribers.

3.6.1 Platform

EUT uses Mailchimp as the email platform to be used for the newsletter design, sending and stats monitoring. Mailchimp allows to easily create newsletters of varying types and then provides simple options for sharing them on social networks such as X or Facebook.

3.6.2 Audience

EUT created the LIFE PRISTINE's Community of Interest. The database of subscribers is being built during the whole project and is being gained progressively via a signup form published on the website homepage and promoted via social media channels, as well as partners' channels.

This signup form complies with GDPR, linking to the project's privacy policy and informing the user about its right to cancel the subscription at any time.

Figure 21. Community of interest signup form

3.6.3 Content

EUT is responsible for the content of newsletters issues, with the contribution of all partners. Before every publication, partners may be contacted for inputs (e.g. information on project tasks or events where the project was presented).

The content of the newsletters follows project milestones. Every issue includes the appropriate references to the LIFE Programme and contact details (e-mail and link to the website and social media).

3.6.4 Analytics

Newsletter analytics, such as open rate or click through rate, are extracted through Mailchimp. Statistics will be checked 3 days after sending the newsletter and will be analysed in order to see which articles worked best and be able to improve the newsletter impact in the following issues.

4 PRISTINE Dissemination Plan (PDP)

4.1 Exhibitions, fairs and congresses

Participation in national and international conferences and trade shows is essential in order to reach large industrial and scientific sectors. A wide range of venues are suitable for the exhibition and publication of the LIFE PRISTINE results, relating to project topics.

Dissemination mainly focuses on partners countries (Spain, Germany, and the Netherlands) but partners have also considered attending events taking place in other European countries and across the EU borders, targeting communities strongly related to the project objectives, certainly including academia and the water sector.

4.1.1 Attended dissemination events

Up to M23, partners have disseminated LIFE PRISTINE in different events, including exhibitions targeting the industrial community, such as AEDyR’s International Congress or the 3rd Congress of Spanish Young Water Professionals.

Table 11. Attended events (M1-M23)

DATE	EVENT	AUDIENCE	LOCATION	PARTNER	DESCRIPTION
November 16-19, 2022	3 rd Congress of Spanish Young Water Professionals	Industry community	Valencia, Spain	ACCIONA	Presentation of the LIFE PRISTINE project, focusing on the project’s objectives, technology and demonstration scenarios MORE INFO
February 1, 2023	ISLE-iAgua Utilities Webinar Series	Industry community	Online	ACCIONA	Presentation of the project during the webinar “Microcontaminants: how to manage them” MORE INFO
February 10, 2023	100tífiques	Civil society	Granollers, Spain	ACCIONA	Introduction of LIFE PRISTINE during a talk to a group of 60 high-school students from the Anna Mogas School-Institute. MORE INFO
March 15-16, 2023	XV Jornadas Técnicas de Reutilización de Agua Regenerada. Nuevos retos, nuevas soluciones	Industry community	Cartagena, Spain	ACCIONA	Inclusion of LIFE PRISTINE information during the presentation “Pursuing the elimination of emerging contaminants in the water cycle”, MORE INFO
May 10, 2023	Webinar on the LIFE Programme 2023 call	General public	Online	ACCIONA	Presentation of the success story of LIFE PRISTINE in the webinar “LIFE Call 2023 main priorities” MORE INFO

May 30-31, 2023	IDEAS 2023	Industry community	Bilbao, Spain	ACCIONA	<p>Presentation of the project, entitled “LIFE PRISTINE. Solution for the elimination of emerging contaminants in water treatment systems”</p> <p>MORE INFO</p>
June 13-15, 2023	XIII AEDYR International Congress	Industry community	Granada, Spain	ACCIONA	<p>Inclusion of LIFE PRISTINE information within the presentation “Innovative and Versatile Integrated Solution to Remove Contaminants of Emerging Concern in Water Treatment Systems”.</p> <p>MORE INFO</p>
June 26-29, 2023	6th IWA International Conference on eco-Technologies for Wastewater Treatment	Industry community	Girona, Spain	ACCIONA	<p>Exhibition of the poster “Innovative and versatile integrated solution to remove contaminants of emerging concern in water treatment systems”, that recaps the main results of the LIFE PRISTINE project to date.</p> <p>MORE INFO</p>
March 19, 2024	Scientific communication workshop organised by the Catalan Water Partnership (CWP)	Industry community	Barcelona, Spain	EUT	<p>Presentation of the communication strategy implemented in LIFE PRISTINE.</p> <p>MORE INFO</p>
June 5-7, 2024	XXXVII Congreso AEAS	Industry community	Castellón, Spain	ACCIONA	<p>General overview of the project with a presentation entitled “LIFE PRISTINE: Removing emerging contaminants from water treatment systems”</p> <p>MORE INFO</p>
June 16-19, 2024	IWA YWP Conference 2024	Scientific and academic community	Prague, Czech Republic	ACCIONA	<p>Project presentation: “Towards an innovative solution to remove contaminants of emerging concern in water treatment systems”</p> <p>MORE INFO</p>
June 24-28, 2024	LET2024: 19th IWA Leading Edge	Scientific and	Essen, Germany	XYLEM, ACCIONA	<p>Inclusion of LIFE PRISTINE information in the poster</p>

	Conference on Water and Wastewater Technologies	academic community			“Photolytic Ozonation As Promising Alternative AOP Using UV-LEDs”
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4.1.2 Planned dissemination events

Project partners will continue to target national and international conferences, congresses and workshops participated by the academic community to transfer the knowledge acquired during the project. Project partners will also connect with the water sector in national and international congresses, exhibitions and fairs to disseminate the benefits and potential of LIFE PRISTINE solution.

Table 12. Planned events

DATE	EVENT	AUDIENCE	LOCATION	PARTNER	TYPE OF DISSEMINATION
September 18-19, 2024	XIV Jornadas de Comunicación y Divulgación Científicas	General public	Barcelona, Spain	ACCIONA	To be determined
September 23-29, 2024	Nit de la Recerca 2024	General public	Barcelona, Spain	ACCIONA	Workshop
March 16-20, 2025	14th IWA International Conference on Water Reclamation and Reuse	Scientific and academic community	Cape Town, South Africa	XYLEM	To be determined
To be determined	Meeting of young professionals from companies of the Board of Trustees of The Princess of Girona Foundation	To be determined	To be determined	ACCIONA	To be determined

A non-exhaustive list of events already identified as relevant to continue disseminating LIFE PRISTINE activities and outcomes are presented in table 13. The list will be periodically updated by partners.

Table 13. Events of interest

Name	Typology	Dates next edition	City	Country
World Water Congress	Congress & Exhibition	August 2024	Toronto	Canada
Stockholm Water Week	Congress	August 2024	Stockholm	Sweden
Aqua Tech Mexico	Exhibition	September 2024	Mexico City	Amsterdam

WEFTEC	Exhibition & Conference	October 2024	New Orleans	United States
IWA Digital Water Summit	Congress & Exhibition	November 2024	Bilbao	Spain
Membrane Technology	Conference & exposition	February 2025	Long Beach	United States
IEEXPo	Trade fair	April 2025	Shanghai	China
SETAC Europe	Conference	May 2025	Vienna	Austria
Water Innovation Europe	Conference	June 2025	Brussels	Belgium
IFAT	Trade fair	May 2026	Munich	Germany

4.2 Networking activities

Wide and transversal dissemination of project activities and results is crucial to maximise impact and level of engagement across all identified stakeholders.

For this purpose, this task will involve participation, the setting up and organisation of project meetings, technical forums/workshops and conferences not only to raise awareness of LIFE PRISTINE, but also create a link with emerging European, regional and national initiatives, ensuring collaboration with them to increase project’s long-term sustainability.

4.2.1 Workshops

Attending and organizing workshops has been recognised as a key activity to share the project’s results and create synergies among other similar projects, potential customers and partners, as well as open up the project’s results to the specialised audience interested in the project’s innovative technology.

Partners agreed on organising **2 workshops during the project’s last year** to disseminate the project results at important events in the industrial sector. Partners will be responsible to present the project outputs and share the know-how generated during the project with the academic/scientific and industrial community.

The main objectives of the workshops are:

- To introduce potential end-users with the technology and expected benefits.
- To receive feedback from the potential end-users in order to increase its replicability and possible success on the market.
- To learn from the recommendations from the potential end-users and accelerate take-ups of the new technology.

4.2.2 Related project exchanges

Connections with other projects, initiatives and knowledge hubs with complementary interests will be sought at national, EU and international level with the aim of enhancing synergies while avoiding duplication of efforts in the dissemination of results.

Partnering with other projects and initiatives will allow to join efforts and also have a stronger voice when communicating with target audiences.

Additionally, partners will actively interact with the initiatives promoted by these groups and contribute with content on the project to feed associations’ newsletters and publications, when possible. A total of 8 networking meetings during the project are envisaged.

Some of the LIFE PRISTINE related projects and initiatives identified to date, dealing with increasing efficiency of CECs removal, are listed in table 14.

Table 14. LIFE PRISTINE related projects

LIFE PRISTINE related projects	
LIFE SOuRCE (ending 2025)	The objective is to demonstrate an innovative cost-efficient and versatile remediation solution for PFAS contaminated groundwater.
LIFE PHOENIX (ending 2024)	LIFE-PHOENIX is aimed at developing low-cost innovative technologies for WW agricultural reuse
SCENARIOS H2020 (ending 2025)	The objective is to demonstrate a comprehensive set of technological solutions to address the detection, (bio)monitoring, long-term toxicity, risk assessment, pollution control and remediation of PFAs as a test bed for zero pollution ambition from refractory and mobile organic chemicals.
PROMISCES H2020 (ending 2025)	The objective is to develop new analytical methods and toxicological tools to provide data on persistent mobile (PM) substances (i.e., PFAS) in the soil-sediment-water system.
EMPEREST (ending 2025)	The project EMPEREST tests advanced treatment technology that helps water utilities and companies better remove organic micropollutants such as PFAS or pharmaceuticals from wastewater.

4.2.3 Local info-days

A local info-day will be celebrated on each demonstration site where the LIFE PRISTINE Pilot Plant will be installed. The objective of these events is to present project progress and achievement to local stakeholders, gathering specific inputs to create enabling framework for LIFE PRISTINE.

Table 15. Local info-days schedule

LIFE PRISTINE local info-days	
WWTP	M35
DWTP	M46

4.2.4 Final event

A final event will be organized at the end of the project for a publicly presentation of the project results (M48) among key stakeholders (academic/scientific and industrial community). Partners will decide whether hosting the event in one of the consortium countries or within a key congress/conference (see Table 13).

Partners aim at gathering about 200 attendees, including members from key specialised media outlets. The event will be open to all interested parties and promoted throughout LIFE PRISTINE and partners communication channels, but partners will also send private invitations to key contacts in their portfolio. **EUT will be the main responsible partners for the organization of the event, which will include also the contribution of all partners.**

4.3 Scientific publications

Reports or outcomes resulting from the project activities will be published in scientific journals related to the project’s fields. During the project period **at least four publications in international journals are planned.**

As the appearance of results and technical maturity is not yet exactly plannable, the schedule of these actions is flexible being controlled by EUT and follows the work package plan.

During the periodic meetings of the WP leaders relevant results will be discussed and partners, timing set and journals chosen. The type of journals shall be related to the matter of results, such as Environmental Science and Technology or Water Practice and Technology IWA Publishing.

A LIFE PRISTINE Zenodo community has been created to allocate all LIFE PRISTINE-related research publications and materials. Publications will be also published in researchers’ Research Gate pages, whenever applicable.

Figure 22. LIFE PRISTINE Zenodo community

Before any publication of LIFE PRISTINE results, partners will contact the project coordinator, the Dissemination Manager and Exploitation Manager to verify if these do not infringer IP rights.

Before submitting any paper for publication, it is necessary to inform the consortium and show what is going to be presented publicly, so every partner agree on the content.

Each partner will ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer reviewed scientific publications submitted and published via **gold open access whenever available** (provided via the published when an article is published) and/or **green open access** via an online repository to ensure a long-term preservation and availability of the publication.

The Project Coordinator will be responsible for final decisions regarding open access publications. Although gold open access options will be preferred, partners have a small budgetary allocation to ensure open access in case journals' policies are restrictive.

An list of open-access journals of interest for publishing LIFE PRISTINE results was defined, as follows:

Table 16. Open-access journals of interest

Journal name	Link
Environmental Science and Technology	https://pubs.acs.org/journal/esthag
Environmental Modelling and Software	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/environmental-modelling-and-software
<i>Journal of Hazardous Materials</i>	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-hazardous-materials
<i>Environmental Pollution</i>	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/environmental-pollution
<i>Chemosphere</i>	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/chemosphere
<i>Ozone Science & Engineering</i>	https://www.tandfonline.com/loi/bose20
<i>Water Practice and Technology IWA Publishing</i>	https://iwaponline.com/wpt

On the other hand, partners will consider the submission of papers to the **Open Research Europe**, an innovative open access publishing platform offering rapid publication and open peer review.

4.3.1 KPIs reporting

Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the next update of this deliverable, scheduled for M48, as well as in interim progress reports.

In addition, to facilitate the reporting, an Excel file was prepared to record the monthly KPIs progress. The file, stored in the WP8 folder in the Microsoft Teams online repository, contains different tabs, including:

LIFE PRISTINE Media impacts						
Date	Media	Title	Type	Specialised outlet?	Link	
13/10/2022	Filtration + Separation	NX Filtration Joins European initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources	Online	Yes	Link	
12/10/2022	Water & Wastewater Asia	NX Filtration to be part of Acciona-led initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants from water sources	Online	Yes	Link	
11/10/2022	Obras Urbana	Iniciativa para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Yes	Link	
09/10/2022	Aqua Tech	EU COLLABORATION LINKS MEMBRANES & AI TO TARGET EMERGING POLLUTANTS	Online	Yes	Link	
07/10/2022	TecnoAqua	Acciona lidera una iniciativa para eliminar contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Yes	Link	
06/10/2022	FuturENVIRO	ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para la eliminación de contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Yes	Link	
06/10/2022	Aguasresiduales.info	ACCIONA lidera una iniciativa para la eliminación de Contaminantes Emergentes en el Ciclo Integral del Agua	Online	Yes	Link	
05/10/2022	Smart Water Magazine	ACCIONA leads an initiative to eliminate emerging pollutants in end-to-end water cycle	Online	Yes	Link	
05/10/2022	iAqua	Acciona lidera una iniciativa para eliminar contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Yes	Link	
05/10/2022	Retema	Acciona lidera una iniciativa para eliminar contaminantes emergentes en el ciclo integral del agua	Online	Yes	Link	

Figure 25. View of the table to report media impacts